

Cs₂CO₃/Ca/Al multilayer cathode for enhancing the green Polymer Light-Emitting Diodes

Yan Kuin Su, M.V. Madhava Rao^{*}, T.S. Huang and Chun-Yuan Huang

Institute of Microelectronics and Department of Electrical Engineering,
National Cheng Kung University, Tainan 701, Taiwan, ROC.

*Email: madhavmora@yahoo.com

The polymer electronics is an emerging technology having great potential for cost effective, thin, flexible, full color displays and plastic electronics. Some of the issues related to physics, engineering, stability and life time of the devices are still receiving under intensive study(1-4).

In the present work, the fabrication of high brightness(over 30,000 cd/m²) of green polymer light-emitting diodes(PLEDs) based on 2,3-dibutoxy-1,4-poly(phenylene vinylene) (DB-PPV) is improved by introducing a thin layer of Cesium Carbonate(Cs₂CO₃) between the calcicum and the DB-PPV layer(4,5). In comparision to the conventioal device with Ca/Al as the cathode, the performance of the PLED with Cs₂CO₃/Ca/Al cathode, reduced turn-on voltage, highly increased brightness and efficiency. These improvements are attributed to use of an efficient multilayer Cs₂CO₃/Ca/Al electron injection contact that also prevents the formation of Ca diffusion in PLEDs with Ca/Al.

References:

- 1). C.W. Tang, SA. Vanslyke, Appl. Phys. Lett. 51, 913, (1987)
- 2). X. Gong, S. Wang, D. Moses, G.C. Bazan, A. J. Heeger, Adv. Mater., 17, 2053,(2005)
- 3). Y. Xu, J. Peng, J. Jiang, W. Xu, W. Yang, Y. Cao, Appl. Phys. Lett., 87, 193502(2005).
- 4). J. Huang, G. Li, E. Wu, Q. Xu, Y. Yang, Adv. Mater., 18, 114(2006).
- 5). M.L. Tu, Y.K. Su, S.J. Chang, T.H. Fang, W.H. Chen and H. Yang, Japanese, J. Appl. Phys.,44, 2787(2005).